

Atmospheric Temperature and Consumer Rejection of Remote Thermostat Control ^{*}, [†], [‡], [§], [¶]

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Abstract: Wi-Fi-enabled “smart” thermostats are thought to hold substantial potential for managing peak domestic electricity demand. But under what atmospheric conditions will a consumer accept an energy supplier’s remote control of their home heating, ventilation, and air conditioning (HVAC) system? We analysed historical data on 231,344 instances wherein Octopus Energy U.S., an electricity retailer, remotely enacted time-limited changes (≈ 1 -150 minutes) to the heating and cooling set points of its customers’ thermostats (a sample of 1,159 Texan households; 1,834 thermostats). We show that internal temperature, external temperature, and time combine to produce a powerful gradient along which customers’ propensity to endure retailer control varies. Specifically, non-causal estimates from Bayesian multilevel models of the time until customers override their modulated set points indicate that — when external atmospheric conditions are contextually severe (i.e., 10-30°F and 90-110°F) — the survival (i.e., override-free) probability can fall to as low as $\approx 71\%$ over the course of 150 minutes. However, results also suggest that counterbalancing external conditions by changing the internal temperature of a customer’s home prior to spells of set-point modulation (i.e., pre-cooling/heating) could see survival probabilities remain as high as ≈ 90 -97% over 150 minutes. Definitive conclusions necessitate causal inference via field experimentation.

Keywords: Direct Load Control; Price Incentives; Smart Thermostats; Survival Analysis

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[§]We treat this report as a “living” document. Therefore, it may be updated and expanded in the future as our thinking evolves or to correct errors. The date of the last update is given above.

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1 Introduction

In 2020, Octopus Energy Group (OEG) entered the North American market by acquiring Evolve, an energy-optimisation start-up.¹ This venture ultimately saw Evolve become Octopus Energy U.S. (OEUS). And, after the 2022 acquisition of Brilliant Energy, an American retailer, OEG has amassed thousands of customers in Texas (Toplensky, 2024)² — the largest producer of electricity in the United States and a leader in the generation of wind and solar power on par with California (Davies, 2024; U.S. Energy Information Administration, 2023, June 15).

One of OEUS' most intriguing products is *Intelligent Octopus for Thermostats* (IOT). Launched in 2022, IOT is, as of 2024, a “smart add-on feature” for pre-pay and pay-as-you-go 12-month electricity tariff contracts. IOT's unique selling point is that it offers a fixed, location-dependent discount on a customer's all-hours unit price (\$/kWh) in exchange for granting OEUS permission to influence one's home climate in a manner that is, in principle, unnoticeable. Specifically, an IOT customer allows OEUS to remotely adjust their personal thermostat's “set point” for both heating and cooling by three degrees Fahrenheit (°F) for a fixed-length of time (e.g., 30 minutes). This arrangement is distinct from direct shutdown of a customer's heating, ventilation, and air conditioning (HVAC) system. Instead, OEUS merely “holds” a customer's preferred set point 3°F higher (cooling) or lower (heating), regulating the internal temperature that their HVAC system targets in terms of its operation.

Crucially, OEUS modulates set points when electricity is expensive to procure. Thus, IOT is expected to ease grid burden and business expense. This is especially so as IOT customers agree to be subjected to multiple “energy conservation events” on the same day spaced at least 15 minutes apart. Nevertheless, if the internal temperature of a customer's home rises above or falls below the 3°-modified set points, OEUS does not prevent re-engagement of one's HVAC system. Furthermore, IOT customers can themselves “override” (i.e., instantly overturn; reject) their modulated set points during a conservation event, resulting in an inter-event reprieve of at least 60 minutes. However, at present, customers who override more than five events during one month (or disconnect their thermostat for more than 24 hours) forfeit their discounted electricity unit price during the corresponding billing cycle, incentivising compliance with OEUS' interventions. Per May 2024 *Electricity Facts Labels* — i.e., consumer transparency documents mandated by the *Public Utility Council of Texas*, a regulator — IOT's location-dependent discount ranges from ≈\$0.01–0.03/kWh. And all-hours unit prices themselves run from ≈\$0.11–0.13/kWh, depending on location and ignoring sales taxes and standing charges by Texas' various transmission and distribution service providers.³

Of course, OEUS is not the only entity to remotely control Texans' thermostats (Brodkin, 2021; Lyons, 2021; Simon, 2021; Webb & de Luna, 2021). Indeed, the Electric Reliability Council of Texas (ERCOT) — the nonprofit corporation behind Texas' main power grid covering ≈75% of the state's land area — has broadly called for residents to adjust their set points to conserve power when demand is high and temperatures are severe (Webb & de Luna, 2021). Power draw in Texas is sensitive to temperature extremes during winter and summer. And historical reporting by ERCOT (Herbert, 2018, p. 3-4) attributes around 50% of peak grid load during these two seasons to residential energy demand, presumably for the purposes of heating and cooling. Therefore, there is a strong imperative for Texas' various energy suppliers to remotely manage thermostats in private residences.

Beyond Texas, amongst scientists focused on future energy systems, there is substantial interest in melding power grids with information and communication technologies (ICTs) that can be remotely managed via Wi-Fi (Richter & Pollitt, 2018). In brief, these devices are viewed as a promising means of facilitating demand

¹Jackson, G. (2020). *Octopus Energy Enters USA with Acquisition of...Startup Evolve Energy*. *Octopus Energy Blog*.

²Cheam, P. (2021, May 10). *Octopus Energy U.S. Inks Deal to Acquire Brilliant Energy*. *Business Wire*.

³The charges levied on Texans by their transmission and distribution service providers (TDSPs) are a combination of a delivery fee per kWh and a monthly metering fee. OEUS' May 2024 *Electricity Facts Labels* indicate that unit delivery fees range from ≈\$0.04–0.06/kWh, with monthly TDSP fees ranging from \$0.00 (Lubbock Power & Light; LPL) to \$7.85 (Texas-New Mexico Power; TNMP).

side management (DSM) — i.e., the intentional manipulation of patterns of energy consumption in relation to its timing and overall amount, potentially alongside financial reward for consumers (Richter and Pollitt, 2018, p. 218; Albadi and El-Saadany, 2007, p. 1; Sarran et al., 2021, p. 2; see also Creutzig et al., 2024; Ito et al., 2018; KEMA Inc., 2006; Medlock and Hung, 2022; Merski, 2023; Ögelman, 2021; Tomat et al., 2022; Wildstein et al., 2023). DSM has been discussed in relation to multiple areas of day-to-day life such as transport, the traversal of buildings, food consumption, and land use (Creutzig et al., 2016, 2018, 2022, 2024; Sovacool & Griffiths, 2020). However, demand-response achieved through HVAC-connected thermostats is particularly interesting due to low implementation barriers.

For instance, in commercial and non-residential buildings (e.g., offices, universities), global thermostat adjustment using pre-existing infrastructure for site-wide automation provides a readily-available means of DSM at notable scales (Keskar et al., 2022). And, for private residences, the focus of this research, Wi-Fi-enabled “smart” thermostats sold by firms such as Amazon, Ecobee, Google, and Tado° are perhaps the least expensive way for households to access the consumer benefits of energy suppliers’ “intelligent” demand management via forms of off-site automation (e.g., real-time price triggers). Indeed, domestic smart thermostats cost ≈\$50-300 (£50-230) at the time of writing, ignoring subsidisation. In contrast, ICTs like electric vehicles that are relatively straightforward to adopt (cf. solar panels and heat pumps) and positioned as a means of DSM at scale currently have far higher upfront costs, making access prohibitive for large swathes of society (Sheldon, 2022; Sovacool et al., 2017, 2022, 2023; White & Sintov, 2019).

Nevertheless, prior research suggests that the success of remote thermostat control will depend on aspects of a consumer’s proximate environment (Elnakat et al., 2016; Hargreaves & Middlemiss, 2020; Staffell et al., 2023; White & Sintov, 2019). And, given the importance of local physical climate to electricity demand in the U.S. (Allen et al., 2016; Maia-Silva et al., 2020; Reinhart, 2023; Sarran et al., 2021; Staffell et al., 2023), atmospheric conditions likely play a key role in whether or not a consumer rejects a supplier’s domestic intervention. Thus, here we explore the extent to which there is a correlation (*non-causal association*) between near-surface temperature and customer override of OEUS’ imposed set points.

Our investigation is ultimately premised on the assumption that customer override is undesirable. Following work by Merski (2023), Reinhart (2023), Sarran et al. (2021), Staffell et al. (2023), Tomat et al. (2022), and Wildstein et al. (2023), this is for two reasons — one environmental, one business-related.

First, to the extent that adjusting set points has a negative, causal association with energy usage during some fixed period of time, overrides are expected to impair the efficacy of suppliers’ thermostat-based interventions. Put simply, and depending on how long it occurs after event start (Wildstein et al., 2023), override is expected to weaken or erase reduction in energy consumption.

Second, customer satisfaction is paramount in a business context. And overrides may be a leading indicator of discontent. Such distaste could, in turn, drive a customer to reject a tariff product designed around routine climatic intervention. And, at a large scale, increased customer “churn” could undermine the putative grid benefits of “smart energy services” (Richter & Pollitt, 2018, p. 437) like IOT and the soft constraints they attempt to place on behaviour, again assuming that the association between set-point modulation and energy consumption is negative and causal.

There is survey- and interview-based evidence to suggest that consumers do not necessarily view set-point modulation negatively (see Sarran et al., 2021 for a brief review). However, it should not be assumed that private individuals will universally embrace manipulation of their personal thermostats when they are actually subjected to supplier control. Thus, at least in the present case of OEUS, it is critical to paint a data-driven picture of the acceptability of set-point modulation using information on customers’ observed behaviour. Indeed, survey evidence may be overoptimistic as Sarran et al. (2021, p. 6, Fig. 2) report an override rate of 19.5% specifically for Texas in their study of 6,389 North American homes during 23,352 hours-long demand-response events in August/September 2019. Furthermore, Summer 2021, a particularly warm season (DiSavino, 2021), saw multiple media outlets report that Texans were surprised by — and dissatisfied with — their energy supplier’s remote thermostat control (Brodikin, 2021; Lyons, 2021; Simon, 2021). Such report-

Figure 1: Sampled energy conservation events across Texas, October 2022 to May 2024.

Note: Choropleth depicting the number of OEUS’ energy conservation events in our analytic sample (SI.1.1) across the 376 ZIP Code Tabulation Areas (ZCTAs) of Texas (2020 U.S. Census Boundaries; SI.1.2). The number of events across the ZCTAs range from 2 to 7,613 with a mean of ≈ 615 events per ZCTA (Median = 348)

ing is noteworthy in relation to the important commercial dimension of DSM as retailers will be keen to avoid bad “word of mouth” and negative product sentiment by designing smart energy services in a manner that maximises customer comfort whilst preserving potential for grid benefit.

All in all, clarity around the acceptability of products like IOT necessitate analyses of real override behaviour vis-à-vis atmospheric conditions using large scale, high-resolution data — especially given research suggesting that, in some scenarios, American consumers may blame their utility company for disruption caused by interventions beneficial to energy infrastructure (Mildenberger et al., 2022). Accordingly, here, in this brief, exploratory piece of research, we answer the following question:

1. **Research Question:** Under what atmospheric conditions are OEUS customers expected to “survive” (i.e., endure; tolerate) modulation of their thermostat set points?

2 Analytic Strategy In Brief

In the *Supplementary Information* (SI) at the end of this document, we provide a detailed discussion of our data (SI.1, SI.1.3) and an extensive breakdown of our preferred statistical methods (SI.2). However, here it suffices to say that, to answer our research question, we amassed historical records (October 2022-May 2024) on a sample of $N = 231,344$ “energy conservation events” (Fig. 1) issued to 1,834 smart thermostats owned by 1,159 of OEUS’ Texan customers. And we used information on these events, which we also simply call “holds”, to estimate the probability of a customer rejecting OEUS’ remote control over the course of variable-length spells of set-point modulation under different atmospheric conditions.

To clarify, our data take the form of customer-thermostat-event records $i \in \{1, \dots, N\}$, each of which details a set-point hold intended to last a fixed period of time (≈ 1 -150 minutes). Our outcome variable is the observed length of time T_i (milliseconds scaled to minutes) that some customer A endures from the point at which the heating and cooling set points for their thermostat K are remotely changed by OEUS for the purposes of some event i . The outcome T_i is annotated with a binary indicator for whether or not A overrode imposed set points for event i at some point after i ’s start, thus ending the hold.

Data like T_i have a unique property that disqualifies standard regression modelling. In particular, when a conservation event i is overridden by a customer A , our outcome T_i describes customer A ’s *failure time* — i.e., how long A endured from the moment their set points were changed by OEUS without terminating the climatic intervention i . But, in the absence of override, T_i instead describes A ’s *censoring time* — i.e., the length of time OEUS monitored A ’s thermostat K from the inception of set-point modulation in essence to see if A overrode event i .

Ultimately, censoring is a kind of missing-data problem requiring specialised techniques developed by statisticians working in the social, engineering, and biomedical sciences (Camilleri, 2019). Thus, we make sense of T_i using *survival analysis* (i.e., “event history analysis”, “failure-time analysis”, “duration analysis”). In particular, we utilised survival models for right-censored times until a single, non-repeatable event of the same type (e.g., death; here, override of i). Despite T_i being a positive continuous variable, models of this kind produce probabilities of “surviving” (here, *not* overriding event i) over time.

It is important to highlight two technical aspects of our analysis before proceeding to results.

First, a customer A may be subjected to multiple conservation events on the same day. And whilst different customers may be issued events at or around the same time (e.g., during the same 60-minute, or even 15-minute period), each event is understood to be specific to a customer’s *thermostat*. Indeed, OEUS customers may own multiple event-eligible thermostats K — where customers can override changed set points for one device without ending OEUS’ manipulation of the other thermostats in their home. It is for this reason that we conceive of our data as customer-thermostat-event records.⁴

In SI.2.2, we provide a technical summary of the Bayesian multilevel survival models (Brilleman et al., 2020) we used to account for within-group correlation in T_i due to the hierarchical nature of our data. But, briefly, we rely on varying intercepts (i.e., group-specific parameters) to account for the nesting of events i within customers A alongside the cross-classification of customers, calendar dates D (410 in total), and hours of the day H . By “cross-classification”, we simply mean that the same customer A is issued events on multiple days D whilst multiple customers are subjected to events on the same day, *mutatis mutandis* for customers and hours of the day. We accounted for our highest possible level of grouping — i.e., the regions of Texas — using a four-level categorical variable for the [ERCOT grid load zones](#) that subsume customers’ postal codes (i.e., “Houston”, “North”, “South”, “West”). We did not use thermostat ID K as an intermediate level between events i and customers A . Nor did we use geographic areas based on customer’s postal codes (SI.1.2) as an upper-level of aggregation. This is because the median number of thermostats across the customers in

⁴SI.2.5 provides a very short description of Bayesian inference for non-technical audiences. And SI.2.1 provides an extended discussion of the temporal aspects of OEUS’ conservation events through the lens of survival analysis.

Figure 2: Expected probability of survival over 150 minutes of set-point modulation.

Note: The survival curve was constructed using our “best” multilevel model (Table SI.2) of right-censored failure times and drawn as a step function using 150 equally-spaced points between 0 and 150 minutes. Survival probabilities (scaled by 100 to percentages) are summarised using the posterior mode (i.e., the single value with the highest posterior probability; Black Line), the 68% highest posterior density interval (HDI; Inner Blue Ribbon), the 95% HDI (Red Ribbon), and the 100% HDI (i.e., the entire posterior distribution; Outer Yellow Ribbon). Each HDI (shortest probability) is the continuous range containing X% of values with the highest posterior density, where there may be a range of values with a higher probability over a discontinuous interval (Liu et al., 2015). Survival probabilities are standardised (i.e., the result of averaging the 231,344 survival curves for each observation in our analytic sample). Note well the range of the y-axis which does not start at zero. Axis truncation is used to allow better visualisation of concordance between the parametric and non-parametric curves. The non-parametric fit (Teal Lines) was obtained using the R library “survival” and it is a Kaplan-Meier curve created whilst accounting for within-group correlation due to the clustering of events i within customers A . The “survival” library does not allow multiple clustering terms. Concordance between the Kaplan-Meier curve and the model-based curve is generally good across the entire run of observed conservation-event lengths. It is not unusual for survival curves to exhibit higher uncertainty towards later follow-up times due to the ever-decreasing number of study units “at risk”, whether due to “death”, various kinds of censoring (Leung et al., 1997; SI.2.1), or a smaller subset of study units in the analytic sample with longer longer follow-up times. Figure created with the aid of the R library “ggdist”.

our sample is one (Table SI.1). Similarly, the median number of customers across postal-code areas is two. As a result, nesting thermostat-specific parameters within customer or customer-specific parameters within neighbourhood would suffer from substantial redundancy of levels.

Finally, we did not limit our attention to events that occurred when a customer’s HVAC system was set to “cool” (e.g., see Sarran et al., 2021). OEUS holds thermostats throughout the calendar year. And Texas’ experiences with extreme freezing conditions, as well as the implications of these conditions for grid performance, have been widely commented on (e.g., see Gruber et al., 2022).⁵ Thus, we maintain that the acceptability of set-point modulation when a customer wishes to heat their home and it is cold is just as important as the acceptability of set-point modulation when a customer wishes to cool their home and it is hot. As a result, we jointly analysed events regardless of HVAC operating mode (i.e., “Heat”, “Cool”, “Auto”, “Off”). We addressed this pooling of data explicitly in our statistical modelling (SI.2.6).

⁵Knutson, J. (2024, January 20). How Texas’ power grid weathered the latest freeze. *Axios*.

3 Results

3.1 Expected Survival

Considering all events in our analytic sample, just 6% (i.e., 13,851 events out of 231,344; [Table SI.1](#)) ended due to a customer rejecting set-point modulation. This figure is inconsistent with prior research on override in Texas. Specifically, recall that Sarran et al. (2021, p. 6, Figure 2) report an average override rate of 12.9% across multiple states and 19.5% specifically for Texas in their study on North American thermostats in August/September 2019 (see also KEMA Inc., 2006, p. 50-52, Figure 3-6, Tomat et al., 2022, p. 6, and Wildstein et al., 2023, p. 5, Figure 1). We can make no definitive statement as to why the override rates might differ between our analysis and the analysis of Sarran et al. (2021). However, contributing factors presumably include their focus on longer events during warmer months of the year.

Still, our 6% figure is unconditional. That is, it ignores the timing and the censoring of override as well as customer characteristics and atmospheric conditions. Therefore, [Fig. 2](#) is far more useful. This graphic depicts — from conservation-event start until 150 minutes after set-point modulation — the expected *survival probability* $S(T)$ — i.e., the probability that a customer *will not* override an event i by time t or, alternatively and following Box-Steffensmeier and Jones (2004, p. 13), the proportion of events $i \in N$ expected to not be overridden by time t . Note that [Fig. 2](#) shows what Brilleman et al. (2020, p. 15-16) refer to as a *standardised survival curve*. And it is constructed by averaging the survival probabilities $S_i(T_i)$ for 150 equally-spaced timepoints t for the 231,344 thermostat-specific conservation events $i \in N$ given their observed values for each of our correlates (e.g., internal temperature at event start; [SI.1.3](#)) and their associated customer-, day-, and hour-of-day-specific parameters (i.e., $u_{0,A}$, $u_{0,D}$, and $u_{0,H}$ in [Eq. \(4\)](#) and [Eq. \(5\)](#) in [SI.2.2](#)). Values for $S_i(T_i)$ come from our best-performing model in terms of approximate leave-one-observation-out-of-sample predictive ability (see [SI.2.6](#) as well as [Table SI.2](#)).

Keeping this all in mind, the expected trajectory of survival implied by [Fig. 2](#) is more in line with the analyses of Sarran et al. (2021), KEMA Inc. (2006, p. 50-52, Figure 3-6), Tomat et al. (2022, p. 6), and Wildstein et al. (2023, p. 5, Figure 1). Specifically, the standardised curve suggests that the probability of rejecting an OEUS climatic intervention is expected to increase from approximately 5% circa 25 minutes after set-point modulation to approximately 20% circa 150 minutes after event start.

3.2 Temperature, Time, and Customers' Propensity to Endure

Returning to our research question, what might atmospheric conditions mean for accepting set points imposed by OEUS? [Fig. 3](#) depicts survival curves for various combinations of *ranges* of temperature. As with [Fig. 2](#), survival probabilities $S(T)$ in [Fig. 3](#) are standardised — i.e., the average of $S_i(T_i)$ for 150 equally-spaced timepoints. These averages are taken across those conservation events in our data that have values for internal and external temperature that fall within the ranges used for a given combination. [Fig. 3](#) was built using the most-prevalent temperature combinations in our data ([Table 1](#)).

There appears to be stark differences in the trajectory of customers' propensity to endure imposed set points vis-à-vis climate. Whilst interpreting [Fig. 3](#), note that our “best” model ([Table SI.2](#)) features both **linear and quadratic (i.e., squared) terms** for internal and external temperature as well as a multiplicative interaction between the linear versions of internal and external temperature (see [Table SI.3](#)). Under contextually-moderate external conditions (i.e., 50-70°F), varying internal climate does not appear to translate into radically different survival probabilities. Put alternatively, when outside temperatures are not severe, [Fig. 3](#) suggests that time is the salient factor. However, when it is very hot (i.e., 90-110°F) or very cold (i.e., 10-30°F), the probability of tolerating OEUS' climatic intervention appears to decay notably except when internal temperature counterbalances external temperature (i.e., warm inside-cold outside, cool inside-hot outside). This interplay between internal and external temperature appears to generally hold when it is moderately cold (i.e., 30-50°F) and, to a much lesser degree, when it is moderately warm (i.e., 70-90°F).

Figure 3: Expected probability of survival over 150 minutes of set-point modulation given temperature.

Note: The survival curves were constructed using our “best” multilevel model (Table SI.2) of right-censored failure times and drawn as step functions using 150 equally-spaced points between 0 and 150 minutes. Survival probabilities (scaled by 100 to percentages) are summarised using the posterior mode (i.e., the single value with the highest posterior probability; Black Line) and the 95% highest posterior density interval (HDI; Coloured Ribbon). Each HDI (shortest probability) is the continuous range containing 95% of values with the highest posterior density, where there may be a range of values with a higher probability over a discontinuous interval (Liu et al., 2015). Use of HDIs as opposed to equal-tail (i.e., quantile) intervals can result in a jagged appearance in the curves. Survival probabilities are standardised (i.e., the result of averaging survival curves for all conservation events in our data with values for internal and external temperature that fall within a given combination of temperature intervals per Table 1). We focused on combinations most prevalent in our data. Combinations were created by discretising the observed ranges of internal temperature (36-130°F, Table SI.1) and external temperature (6-112°F) into intervals of 3.5°F and 20°F, respectively. Interval widths roughly correspond to the sample standard deviations. Figure created with the aid of the R library “ggdist”. Note well the range of the y-axis which does not start at zero. Axis truncation is used to allow better visualisation of discordance between the various curves.

Overall, temperature seems to be associated with customer rejection of remote thermostat control — a finding consistent with the analyses of, for instance, KEMA Inc. (2006) and Sarran et al. (2021). More importantly, however, is that Fig. 3 also suggests that the pre-cooling or pre-heating of a customer’s home *may* be a viable means of mitigating the risk of override under more-extreme temperatures.⁶

The protective implication of pre-cooling/-heating can be gleaned from Fig. 3 by comparing the grey survival curves for typical internal temperatures ($\approx 72\text{-}75^\circ\text{F}$) for our sample to either the red curve ($\approx 79\text{-}82^\circ\text{F}$) when it is cold or the dark blue curve ($\approx 65\text{-}68^\circ\text{F}$) when it is hot *within* each panel. Potential benefits (in terms of increased survival) are obvious when it is very hot or very cold (for Texas).⁷

To clarify, a key strength of Bayesian inference is that it provides a distribution of possible values for some unknown model parameter (e.g., a regression coefficient) that can be used to make probabilistic statements about that parameter’s likely value, richly describing uncertainty. This is powerful. And it is distinct from the conclusions one can draw using frequentist confidence intervals which relate to sampling variability across similar, repeated analyses (Cumming & Finch, 2005; Greenland et al., 2016). Thus, it is useful to consider the posterior mode (PM; i.e., the most-probable parameter value; a point summary of posterior centrality)

⁶Griffiths, S. (2023, July 1). Will Texas become too hot for humans? *The BBC*.

⁷We attempted to account for customers’ movement patterns with parameters for hour of the day (Fig. 4). But, ultimately, we do not know whether customers were at home during OEUS’ conservation events. Compared to the grey curves for typical internal temperatures ($\approx 72\text{-}75^\circ\text{F}$) in Fig. 3, we suspect that the somewhat better expected survival when it is cold outside whilst being cool inside (i.e., Blue and Teal Ribbons) or hot outside whilst being warm inside (i.e., Yellow and Red Ribbons) may be related to patterns of physical presence (e.g., leaving the home; not being at home) over the course of conservation events, although we cannot be sure. See also point estimates in Table SI.3 for our linear and quadratic terms.

Table 1: Prevalence of temperature combinations in sample of energy conservation events.

Int. Temp. (°F) at Event Start	Ext. Temp. (°F) 60 Min. Prior to Hour Containing Start of Event							Total
	[-10, 10]	(10, 30]	(30, 50]	(50, 70]	(70, 90]	(90, 110]	(110, 130]	
[33.2, 36.8]	0	3	0	0	0	0	0	3
(36.8, 40.2]	17	25	0	0	0	0	0	42
(40.2, 43.8]	7	17	0	0	0	0	0	24
(43.8, 47.2]	0	5	25	0	0	0	0	30
(47.2, 50.8]	0	16	9	2	2	1	0	30
(50.8, 54.2]	0	44	29	40	66	6	0	185
(54.2, 57.8]	11	74	64	7	4	0	0	160
(57.8, 61.2]	58	306	272	77	45	5	0	763
(61.2, 64.8]	68	901	1,334	441	116	3	0	2,863
(64.8, 68.2]	41	2,179	5,220	3,604	1,019	197	0	12,260
(68.2, 71.8]	33	1,852	5,573	13,970	9,870	4,037	1	35,336
(71.8, 75.2]	8	557	1,684	11,342	37,855	28,976	4	80,426
(75.2, 78.8]	13	85	375	2,240	25,921	43,233	17	71,884
(78.8, 82.2]	0	50	86	241	4,942	16,388	6	21,713
(82.2, 85.8]	0	0	0	16	721	3,156	0	3,893
(85.8, 89.2]	0	0	1	1	147	1,139	0	1,288
(89.2, 92.8]	0	0	0	1	26	333	0	360
(92.8, 96.2]	0	0	0	0	2	62	0	64
(96.2, 99.8]	0	0	0	0	0	11	0	11
(99.8, 103]	0	0	0	0	0	8	0	8
(103, 107]	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
(107, 110]	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
(110, 114]	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
(114, 117]	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
(117, 121]	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
(121, 124]	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
(124, 128]	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
(128, 131]	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1
Total	256	6,114	14,672	31,982	80,736	97,556	28	231,344

Note: Count of energy conservation events in analytic sample for various combinations of ranges of internal temperature at event start and external near-surface temperature during the 60-minute period prior to the hour during which a conservation event began. To adjust for external humidity, models also feature linear and quadratic terms for near-surface dew point temperature (Table SI.3) which is excluded from our combinations for simplicity.

alongside the 95% highest posterior density interval (HDI; i.e., the continuous range of values containing 95% of the posterior distribution) for various points in time in Fig. 3.

Specifically, our “best” model indicates that, over the course of ≈ 150 minutes and when it is very hot outside (Fig. 3, 90-110°F, right-most panel), there is a 95% chance that the probability of *not* overriding a hold will fall within the continuous interval [0.71, 0.73] (95%HDI) given a moderate internal climate (i.e., ≈ 72 -75°F),

Figure 4: Distributions of posterior values for override risk for hour of day (Gold = Higher; Grey = Lower).

Note: Figure depicts deviations $u_{0,H}$ (log hazard scale; y -axis) from the population intercept β_0 (Eqs. (4) and (5) in SI.2.2) for each hour during which OEUS issued the energy conservation events in our analytic sample, October 2022 to May 2024. Under our best-performing model (Tables SI.2 and SI.3), $\beta_0 = -6.70$ (PM; 95%HDI = $[-6.92, -6.47]$) Posterior draws for each group-specific parameter $u_{0,H}$ are summarised using the posterior mode (Black Bullet), the 68% HDI (Inner, Fat Black Vertical Line Range), and the 95% HDI (Outer, Thin Black Vertical Line Range). HDIs are accompanied by the kernel density estimate of the entire distribution of posterior draws for $u_{0,H}$ (Bell Curves). Each posterior distribution is coloured based on the proportion of the signs of each of its constituent values that are greater than zero (i.e., crude directional probability for increased or decreased log hazard of override during a given hour of the day). There is compelling evidence of $u_{0,H}$ being non-zero when the bulk of the posterior distributions falls above or below the dashed line (e.g., 2H, 4H, 16H, 18H, and 20H; cf. 8H, 10H, and 14H). Figure created with the aid of the R library “ggdist”. For discussion of differences between the “hazard” and “survival”, see SI.2.2.

where the most-likely value of the standardised survival probability in this scenario is 0.72 (PM). However, our model also suggests that there is a 95% chance that the probability of survival for a 150-minute event will instead fall within the interval $[0.88, 0.92]$ (PM = 0.90) when internal climate is, relatively speaking, cool (i.e., $\approx 65\text{-}68^\circ\text{F}$). Fig. 3 indicates that pre-heating may be similarly protective when it is very cold outside ($10\text{-}30^\circ\text{F}$), where the 95% HDI is $[0.67, 0.73]$ (PM = 0.71) for the $\approx 72\text{-}75^\circ\text{F}$ internal-temperature range and $[0.95, 0.98]$ (PM = 0.97) for the $\approx 79\text{-}82^\circ\text{F}$ range.⁸

4 Stakeholder Recommendations and Caveats

Here we have explored consumer tolerance of manipulation of their personal HVAC system by an energy supplier in exchange for a discounted electricity price, asking: How might atmospheric conditions shape the acceptability of such an arrangement? To answer this question, we used data on 231,344 instances wherein Octopus Energy U.S. remotely enacted time-limited changes ($\approx 1\text{-}150$ minutes) to the heating and cooling

⁸Under our “best” model, the standard deviation of the group-specific parameters for customer (i.e., $u_{0,A}$ in Eqs. (4) and (5) in SI.2.2) is notable (95%HDI = $[1.20, 1.51]$; PM = 1.30; Table SI.3), suggesting that there is variation in the log hazard of override (i.e., the instantaneous probability of override; SI.2.2) not captured by our covariates that is attributable to customers (i.e., account holders) themselves, *mutatis mutandis* for the parameters specific to hour of day $u_{0,H}$ (95%HDI = $[0.07, 0.28]$; PM = 0.28; Table SI.3; Fig. 4). Such group-specific variation perhaps hints at the potential utility of harnessing non-atmospheric information to craft “optimal-length interventions” by tailoring hold policies to individual customers or specific times of the day. Such an approach is especially interesting in terms of business decision-making as more-personalised hold policies could be used to target an overall decrease in the probability of override and thus more efficacious climatic interventions at scale whilst also ensuring broad-based customer satisfaction (to the extent that override is an indicator of customer discomfort).

set points of its customers' thermostats (a sample of 1,159 Texans). We found that rejecting OEUS control is rare in an absolute sense ($\approx 6\%$ unconditional override rate; Table SI.1). Yet, modelling that accounts for the timing of override suggests that, on average (Fig. 2), the risk of a customer terminating one of OEUS' climatic interventions increases over time to $\approx 20\%$, where the trajectory of this risk differs with indoor and outdoor temperature (Fig. 3).

Formally, and averaging across all 231,344 thermostat holds in our sample, quadrupling the length of a spell of set-point modulation from ≈ 25 minutes to ≈ 100 minutes appears to be associated with a roughly 10-point reduction in the probability of *not* overriding OEUS control (i.e., 95% to 85%; Fig. 2; $95\% \text{HDI}_{\approx 25 \text{ Min.}} = [0.946, 0.948]$; $95\% \text{HDI}_{\approx 100 \text{ Min.}} = [0.845, 0.851]$). Given the nature of the event of study — i.e., override versus actual death — the overall expected probability of survival remains quite palatable, even under the longest conservation events. However, our non-causal modelling also suggests that internal temperature, external temperature, and time combine to produce a powerful gradient along which customers' propensity to endure supplier control can vary. Indeed, when atmospheric conditions are extreme within the context of our Texan sample (i.e., 10-30°F and 90-110°F; Fig. 3, outer panels), survival probabilities appear to have a strong association with internal climate — falling to as low as $\approx 71\%$, or holding as high as $\approx 97\%$, over the course of 150 minutes, depending on internal and external conditions.

What then do our results mean for suppliers such as OEUS and grid operators like ERCOT? Keeping top of mind that our findings are not causal and taking special note of the arguments of IJzerman et al. (2020, Figure 2, p. 1093) around application of behavioural science to policy, there are two upshots.

First, our most interesting results point to the *potential* efficacy of pre-cooling/-heating. And our inferential modelling strongly suggests that changing the temperature of customers' homes immediately prior to the start of a thermostat hold could be a powerful lever that suppliers and grid operators can pull to bolster the probability of the success of their climatic interventions. That said, there will presumably be physical constraints on how much a supplier can shift the internal temperature inside of a customer's home over 60 minutes such that some combinations of atmospheric conditions (Table 1) — and their concomitant protective effects (Fig. 3) — are more realistic than others depending on, for instance, factors related to a home's energy efficiency (e.g., insulation).

Second, we recommend that suppliers and grid operators think carefully about the length of energy conservation events and not simply attribute the possible effects of elapsed time to other factors such as temperature. Taking the timing of override seriously by using survival analysis strikes us as key to deriving actionable business and policy insight into the behaviour of consumers when they are actually subjected to thermostat holds (cf. self-reported willingness to accept supplier control). Indeed, our results suggest that the unconditional override rate (here, just 6%) obscures rich dynamics around how the acceptability of supplier-imposed set points might unfold across the "life" of a hold. And, at least for OEUS, 50-55 minutes is perhaps a "sweet spot" as it is a near doubling of the currently-favoured hold length (30 minutes) whilst appearing to keep the survival (override-free) probability to $\approx 90\%$ (Fig. 2; $95\% \text{HDI}_{\approx 55 \text{ Min.}} = [0.900, 0.904]$). Still, we stress again that clever changes to internal temperature during the 60 minutes prior to the start of a climatic intervention could possibly make even the longest spells of set-point modulation viable in business-relevant scenarios wherein atmospheric conditions are severe and wholesale electricity prices (presumably) high.

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Supplementary Information (SI) for “Atmospheric Temperature and Consumer Rejection of Remote Thermostat Control”

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SI.1 Data Summary

SI.1.1 The Events

For our analysis, we used exceptional administrative records on the functioning of a sample of Ecobee “smart” thermostats owned by American households in Texas who purchase electricity from Octopus Energy U.S. (OEUS). Historical records relate to 343,534 *thermostat-specific* energy conservation events issued by OEUS between October 2022 (i.e., the month of the earliest-recorded events) and May 30, 2024 (i.e., the cut-off for our retrospective analysis) — 18,453 of which ended due to customer override.

We constructed our analytic sample by filtering events based on their temporal characteristics. Specifically, historical records are annotated with information on when OEUS gave the command to start/end set-point modulation — i.e., +3°F to one’s desired cooling set point and -3°F from one’s desired heating set point — as well as when modified set points were in effect. That is, there are timestamps for when a “hold” was actually “set”, organically “released”, or actively overridden by a customer alongside timestamps for when OEUS issued a “hold start” and “hold end” remote command.

OEUS has experimented with a number of thermostat “hold policies” (i.e., target lengths for energy conservation events) since the inception of IOT in 2022. And historical event records with non-missing data for the aforementioned timestamps indicate that, between October 2022 and May 2024, the issued length of holds ranged from seconds to 149 minutes (Table SI.1). In late 2022 and early 2023, OEUS generally issued 120-minute events. And, from early 2023, this appears to have been superseded with a policy of issuing 5-15 minute events. However, from July 2023 to the time of writing, events are intended to be 30 minutes. Still, OEUS has sometime issued events with divergent “off-policy” lengths on “special” occasions and for the purposes of general experimentation. For instance, 149-minute events were issued during a [solar eclipse on October 10, 2023](#). And, in response to spikes in wholesale electricity prices on April 16-17, 2024, IOT customers were subjected to 59-minute events.

Remote control of smart ICTs is not perfect. Indeed, remote commands are subject to unexpected machine error and to latency between command issuance and the point at which a command actually takes effect. As such, the gamut of issued event lengths that appear in the historical data do not neatly reflect OEUS’ history of hold policies (e.g., three minutes, seven minutes, 24 minutes, 111 minutes, etc.). Furthermore, due to latency and machine error, and for conservation events that were not overridden, the elapsed time between remote commands to start and stop set-point modulation (i.e., an event’s “issued duration”) may not match the recorded experienced length of a conservation event for the end user (i.e., “actual event duration”). For example, there are events in the historical records with actual durations (given the available timestamps) that greatly exceed their issued duration (e.g., by hours and even days).

Given these challenges, we took a straightforward approach to building our sample of events, aiming to minimise arbitrary exclusion criteria (Stefan & Schönbrodt, 2023). In particular, we filtered the universe of customer-thermostat-event records by retaining events with non-missing data for the timestamps indicating when remote commands were issued and enacted. Additionally, we retained events with issued durations of any length up to and including the maximum observed in OEUS’ database (i.e., 149 minutes). That said, we only retained an event when its actual duration was less than or equal to its issued duration *plus one minute*. We used a one-minute buffer when comparing actual event duration to issued event duration to allow for machine latency. We consider the width of this buffer to be sensible. But, it is arbitrary. Last, we retained events with actual durations greater than zero — a requirement of survival models.

Our exclusion criteria resulted in a set of 232,971 energy conservation events issued (coordinated universal time) between October 25, 2022 and May 30, 2024. And, after excluding events with missing data for our covariates (e.g., temperature, cooling preferences), we were left with an analytic sample of 231,344 events (Fig. 1). The vast majority of these events were scheduled for 30 minutes or less. Yet, it was vital that we retain data on the longer events in order to probe the acceptance of override under longer climatic interventions,

where the statistical models we used accommodated mixed event lengths.

SI.1.2 The Weather

Internal temperature at the start of each conservation event — as well as customers’ heating and cooling preferences (i.e., their un-modified set points) — were collected by OEUS as a part of the routine remote sensing done by Ecobee thermostats. The OEUS records lack data on motion-sensing, the orientation of override (i.e., Was an event overridden due to a customer increasing or decreasing their set point?), and internal humidity. Due to the absence of information on motion, we do not know at what points in time OEUS customers occupied their home whilst a hold was in effect.

To link data on conservation events with data on atmospheric conditions, we grouped OEUS customers inside scientifically-meaningful geographic units of Texas using their Zone Improvement Plan (ZIP) code (i.e., “postcode”) and the 2021 U.S. Postal Service (USPS) ZIP Code to ZIP Code Tabulation Area (ZCTA) geospatial “crosswalk” file compiled by the [National Studies on Air Pollution and Health research group](#) at Harvard University (Audirac, 2024). ZIP codes are points in space used for package delivery. In contrast, ZCTAs are aggregations of ZIP codes for populated points to areal shapes based on the statistical reporting blocks used by the U.S. Census Bureau for its decennial exercise (Grubestic & Matisziw, 2006; Wilson & Din, 2018). Shapefiles — i.e., data files that store geospatial information — detailing the 2020 boundaries for Texas’ ZCTAs were obtained using the [R library “tigris”](#) (Walker, 2016). ZCTA boundaries and the shapefiles themselves were [derived by the U.S Census Bureau](#).¹ For linkage, we used the ZIP code associated with the [Electric Service Identifier \(ESIID; also “ESID” or “EDI-ID”\)](#) for a customer’s *property’s* physical address (cf., billing ZIP codes). ESIID’s are governed by ERCOT.

Weather data were drawn from the European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts (ECMWF) Re-Analysis 5 (ERA5) dataset (Copernicus Climate Change Service, 2018; Hersbach et al., 2020) which assimilates global historical atmospheric information from 1940 onward. ERA5 records were pulled directly from ECMWF’s free API via the [R library “KrigR”](#) (Kusch & Davy, 2022) using the geographic extent of the U.S. Census Bureau’s 2020 ZCTA shapefiles for Texas. And, with the [R library “extractR”](#), we calculated zonal statistics for relevant ERA5 variables (e.g., temperature) by taking the average of their values across the points of Earth contained within each of Texas’ 2020 ZCTAs for each hour of each day from October 1, 2022 to May 30, 2024.

Hourly ERA5 data, [which are annotated with timestamps in coordinated universal time \(UTC\)](#), were lagged by one period and then joined with OEUS’ historical event data prior to model fitting. Accordingly, our analysis is based on the mean of an atmospheric variable across a customer’s ZCTA during the 60-minute period immediately prior to the hour of the day containing the start of a given conservation event. Note that conservation-event timestamps (i.e., when remote commands were given and enacted) are also recorded in UTC in OEUS’ database. This allowed for the straightforward joining of the event and atmospheric data. However, using the [R library “lubridate”](#), we converted timestamps for when set-point modulation actually took effect to the “America/Chicago” (i.e., “US/Central”) timezone for the purposes of describing/modelling the hours of day during which holds occurred (Fig. 4).

[ERA5 features a number of atmospheric variables at the level of the hour](#), its smallest level of granularity. Following prior work on thermostat override (e.g., KEMA Inc., 2006; Sarran et al., 2021) and research on atmospheric conditions and electricity demand across the U.S. (Allen et al., 2016; Maia-Silva et al., 2020; Staffell et al., 2023), we used two such variables for our analysis:

1. [Near-Surface External Temperature \(2m Temperature\)](#): The estimated temperature (Kelvin) of air two meters above the Earth’s surface at a specific place and time. Prior to model fitting, 2m temperature was converted to °F using the formula: $((^{\circ}K - 273.15) \times (9 \div 5) + 32)$.

¹See: <https://www.census.gov/programs-surveys/geography/guidance/geo-areas/zctas.html>

2. **Near-Surface External Dew Point (2m Dewpoint Temperature):** Dew point temperature is the estimated temperature (Kelvin) at which the air can no longer hold gaseous water (i.e., vapour) due to being fully saturated. Cooling the air below this temperature [leads to the condensation of water vapour into a liquid](#) (i.e., dew). The dew point is an indicator of humidity.² Higher values indicate that there is more moisture in the air and thus greater potential for human discomfort (Heidt, 2024). Prior to model fitting, dew point was also be converted to °F using the formula: $(^{\circ}K - 273.15) \times (9 \div 5) + 32$.

We used each customer’s ZIP code to link their place of residence to its corresponding climate zone as set out by the International Energy Conservation Code (IECC; Antonopoulos et al., 2022). This revealed that the vast majority of events (77%) were issued in areas of Texas with the same zone classification. Consequently, we dropped this variable from our analysis. Instead, we relied on hourly temperature and hourly dew point to capture sub-zonal conditions plus a categorical variable for ERCOT load zone to adjust for regional differences in Texas’ climate.³

SI.1.3 Descriptive Statistics

Table SI.1 depicts summary statistics for the variables used for our regression modelling. In addition to zonal statistics for weather, we also utilised information on event characteristics, customers, and their energy usage, constructing variables for:

1. **HVAC Operating Mode At Event Start:** Categorical variable indicating the orientation of a customer’s HVAC system at the beginning of an energy conservation event (i.e., “Heat”, “Cool”, “Auto”, “Off”).
2. **Internal Temperature (°F) At Event Start:** Positive, continuous variable for room temperature at event start, as recorded by a customer’s Ecobee smart thermostat.
3. **Desired Internal Temperature (°F) At Event Start - Cooling HVAC Trigger:** Positive, continuous variable for the internal cooling temperature targeted by a customer’s HVAC system — i.e., a thermostat’s un-modified cooling set point at event start.
4. **Desired Internal Temperature (°F) At Event Start - Heating HVAC Trigger:** Positive, continuous variable for the internal heating temperature targeted by a customer’s HVAC system — i.e., a thermostat’s un-modified heating set point at event start.
5. **Number of Holds (Any Length) Earlier On Same Day:** Count variable for the number of times that a customer’s set points were changed by OEUS prior to a given conservation event on the same day. Counts reflect events of any length, regardless of the cause of their end (e.g., organic end or override).
6. **OEUS Tenure At Event Issuance:** Positive, continuous variable for the number of hours since the start of a customer’s first tariff contract agreement with Octopus Energy U.S. up until the time at which a given event i was issued. Scaled to years (i.e., Tenure \div 8,760).

²See: https://www.weather.gov/arx/why_dewpoint_vs_humidity

³IECC climate zones are defined at the level of Federal Information Processing Standards (FIPS) counties — i.e., political/administrative areas of the United States. ZIP codes were linked to FIPS counties using the U.S. Department of Housing and Urban Development-USPS geospatial “crosswalk” files for 2021 (Wilson & Din, 2018). Customers in our analytic sample lived in counties with IECC climate zone classifications of “1A (Very Hot Humid)”, “2A (Hot Humid)”, “2B (Hot Dry)”, “3A (Warm Humid)”, or “3B (Warm Dry)”. Of the events in our analytic sample, 77% were issued to customers residing in “Hot Humid” counties. Antonopoulos et al. (2022) provide a discussion of how IECC climate zones map to those defined by the U.S. Department of Energy Building America Program which promotes the energy efficiency of residential buildings.

7. **Hold Tenure At Event Issuance:** Positive, continuous variable for the number of hours since the start of a customer’s first-ever energy conservation event up until the time at which a given event i was issued. Scaled to years (i.e., $Tenure \div 8,760$).
8. **Total Hourly Electricity Consumption (kWh):** Positive, continuous variable for the sum of a customer’s electricity consumption across available quarter-hourly meter readings comprising the 60-minute period immediately prior to the hour during which a given event i began.
9. **Electricity Reliability Council of Texas (ERCOT) Grid Load Zone:** The geographic region of Texas’s power grid encapsulating a customer’s property’s postal code. ERCOT load zones play an important role in the setting of wholesale electricity prices and delivery of power to Texans.

Note that our models were fit using parameters specific to each of the 410 calendar dates in our analytic sample (SI.2.2) in order to (try to) capture time-specific peculiarities in OEUS’ rules around override. This is important for 120-minute conservation events issued in late 2022/early 2023 for the launch of *Intelligent Octopus for Thermostats* which differ from those under latter hold regimes in a fashion that is likely to influence how customers approach override in general. Indeed, the launch regime might be described as more “permissive” of override due to differences in: (a) how customers were notified about set-point modulation; and (b) the rules around remuneration. In particular, notification about 120-minute events was sent to customers’ mobile phones via SMS and via “push” alerts in the Octopus Energy mobile application. Furthermore, OEUS aimed to issue just one 120-minute event to a thermostat per day. In contrast, OEUS now issues multiple, shorter events on the same day and customers are sometimes notified via less-salient non-push messages in the mobile application and on the [display for their smart thermostat\(s\)](#).

Table SI.1: Summary statistics for energy conservation events (N = 231,344), October 2022 to May 2024.

Characteristic	Mean (SD) [Minimum, 5%, Median, 95%, Maximum]; N (%)
Actual Event Duration (Minutes)	29.61 (19.00) [0.00, 13.71, 29.85, 32.43, 150.46]
Hold Overridden	—
No (Num. Conservation Events w/ Censored Times)	217,493 (94.01%)
Yes	13,851 (5.99%)
Hold Policy (OEUS Issued Event Duration)	—
0-3 Minute Holds (Off-Policy Lengths)	730 (0.32%)
4-15 Minute Holds (Early 2023; Experimentation)	39,698 (17.16%)
16-26 Minute Holds (Off-Policy Lengths)	1,030 (0.45%)
27-29 Minute Holds (Status Quo From July 2023)	175,537 (75.88%)
41-49 Minute Holds (Off-Policy Lengths)	2,999 (1.30%)
56-59 Minute Holds (Special Events: April-May 2024 Price Spikes)	1,292 (0.56%)
111-120 Minute Holds (Launch Regime; Late 2022-Early 2023)	9,573 (4.14%)
146-149 Minute Holds (Special Events: October 14, 2023 Solar Eclipse)	485 (0.21%)
Internal Temperature (°F) at Event Start	74.42 (4.23) [36.20, 67.40, 74.70, 80.60, 129.70]
Near-Surface External Temperature (°F) 60 Min. Prior to Event Hour	81.15 (20.20) [6.24, 39.30, 85.89, 103.59, 112.04]
Near-Surface External Dew Point (°F) 60 Min. Prior to Event Hour	60.43 (16.58) [-10.91, 27.33, 66.36, 76.84, 81.73]
Desired Internal Temperature (°F) - Cooling HVAC Trigger	75.32 (3.43) [55.00, 70.00, 75.00, 82.00, 98.00]
Desired Internal Temperature (°F) - Heating HVAC Trigger	67.57 (4.29) [45.00, 60.00, 68.00, 74.00, 89.00]
HVAC Operating Mode at Event Start	—
Cool	115,543 (49.94%)
Auto	85,151 (36.81%)
Heat	18,519 (8.00%)
Off	12,131 (5.24%)
Number of Holds (Any Length) Earlier On Event Day	1.85 (2.47) [0.00, 0.00, 1.00, 7.00, 59.00]
Hold Tenure at Event Issuance - Years	0.40 (0.33) [0.00, 0.01, 0.34, 1.02, 1.60]
OEUS Tenure at Event Issuance - Years	0.91 (0.87) [0.00, 0.04, 0.58, 2.60, 5.11]
Total Electricity Consumption (kWh) 60 Min. Prior to Event Hour	2.84 (2.78) [0.00, 0.02, 2.14, 7.96, 30.54]
ERCOT Grid Load Zone	—
Houston	102,682 (44.38%)
North	92,080 (39.80%)
South	24,445 (10.57%)
West	12,137 (5.25%)

Note: 1,159 Customer Account Numbers (Median Conservation Events Per Account: 99; Median Overrides Per Account: 4); 1,834 Thermostat IDs (Median Thermostats Per Account: 1); 410 Calendar Days of Events (Median Conservation Events Per Date: 182); 376 ZCTAs (Median Accounts Per ZCTA: 2); 64 FIPS Counties (Median Accounts Per County: 2).

SI.2 Methods

SI.2.1 Time to Override

Our data take the form of customer-thermostat-event records i detailing set-point “holds” (also, “energy conservation events”) intended to last fixed periods of time. Our outcome variable is the observed length of time T_i that some customer A endures once the heating and cooling set points for A ’s thermostat K are remotely changed by OEUS for the purposes of event i . The outcome T_i is annotated with a binary indicator for whether or not A overrode event i at some point after i ’s start.

Formally, the nonnegative variable T_i is the elapsed time between two timestamps. The first is the point at which thermostat K ’s set points are *actually* changed by OEUS (cf. the timestamp for when the remote command is given). We take this as the moment from which customer A is “at risk” of overriding conservation event i for the specific thermostat K . The second timestamp reflects one of three conservation-event-ending occurrences. These are: (a) the organic termination of i as pre-determined/controlled by OEUS; (b) termination of i due to machine error (e.g., the premature issuing of an event-ending command); or (c) termination of i due to active customer override (i.e., the timestamp for the point of “death”).⁴

Answering our research question necessitated a model of the third event-ending occurrence. And, when we speak of the “time until an event”, we mean the elapsed observation time (i.e., not calendar time) until override. However, recall from the *Main Text* (Section 2) that data like T_i have a unique property that disqualifies standard regression modelling. In particular, when a conservation event i is overridden by a customer A , T_i describes A ’s *survival/failure time* — i.e., how long A endured from the moment their set points were changed by OEUS without rejecting the climatic intervention. But, in the absence of override, T_i instead describes a customer’s *censoring time* — i.e., the length of time A was monitored by OEUS in essence to see if they overrode event i for thermostat K .

Practically speaking, censoring means that one’s true survival time T_i^* is unknown but assumed to be greater than the observed time of censoring T_i (Leung et al., 1997, p. 84-85). Thus, when customers do not override their modulated set points, we only know that these individuals did not reject OEUS control up until the scheduled end of a conservation event i . When using survival-analytic nomenclature, the elapsed time from the inception of set-point modulation to this scheduled end is known as the *follow-up time* and it is mechanically equal to OEUS’ issued event length. Similarly, when an event ends due to mechanical error, we only know that a customer did not reject OEUS control during event i up until the moment of technical fault. Note well that censoring is different from *truncation*, the latter of which would imply that T_i^* could never be greater than T_i .⁵

All in all, our data suffer from two types of censoring — i.e., *right-point end-of-study censoring* and *right-point lost-to-follow-up censoring* (Leung et al., 1997, p. 87-88). The former is fully determined by OEUS and whatever length of time it chooses for a given conservation event. And, in the present scenario, right-point end-of-study censoring simply indicates that a customer “survived” the entire length of some event i issued to some thermostat K (cf. “common” censoring whereby all conservation events for all thermostats would be scheduled to end at the same moment in time; see Leung et al. 1997, p. 92-93). In contrast, lost-to-follow-up censoring occurs when a study unit does not “survive” the entire length of the follow-up period for a reason

⁴Recall from the *Main Text* (Section 1) that if the internal temperature of a customer’s home rises above (cooling) or falls below (heating) the 3°-modified set points, OEUS does not prevent the re-engagement of one’s HVAC system. Indeed, the supplier-imposed set points remain in place until the organic end of i , as pre-arranged by OEUS. Accordingly, in those cases wherein the internal temperature of one’s home breaches the 3°-modified set points, OEUS considers event i to *not have been* terminated pre-maturely.

⁵Recall that the same customer can have multiple thermostats that are independently issued successive conservation events by OEUS. Accordingly, we could have also approached our analysis through the lens of survival models for repeated events of the same type. However, we opted for a simple analysis focused on one event type and the termination of individual thermostat holds as this is most relevant to consumers of our research. For discussion of survival models for repeated events, see Box-Steffensmeier and Jones (2004) and Hougaard (2000).

not related to the principal event of interest. For instance, censoring of this form would occur if a patient were to suffer a fatal heart attack in a study of time to death after being diagnosed with cancer. Here, lost-to-follow-up censoring occurs when i ends pre-maturely due to machine error.

Again, censoring is a kind of missing data problem requiring specialised techniques. And it is for this reason that we used survival analysis to model failure times T_i . We note two major methodological assumptions with respect to censoring:

1. **An Event (Override) Is Possible:** For all known sources of censoring for our analysis, it is assumed that were a conservation event to instead continue on for some arbitrary length of time (e.g., hours, days, weeks), customers would indeed eventually reject OEUS' imposed thermostat set points. This implies that the true survival time for a given event i is greater than its censoring time or, rather, $T_i^* > T_i$. Furthermore, this assumption implies that times to override are not infinite. And, practically speaking, it obviates the need for a special class of survival models called “cure” or “split-population” models which are used when some proportion of one's sample will never experience the event of interest. See Amico and Van Keilegom (2018) for an introduction to and review of cure models.
2. **Censoring Times are Non-Informative:** Second, it is assumed that censoring times are (conditionally) independent of event times — i.e., that the time of censoring is *non-informative* with respect to the timing of override. By informative, we mean that “...censoring provides more information than the fact that survival time exceeded a certain time” (Leung et al., 1997, p. 85). And it is possible that there are third variables (i.e., the aforementioned “more information”) related to machine error that determine: (a) whether a customer is lost to follow up; as well as (b) their propensity to override. That said, all customers in our analytic sample have thermostats manufactured by Ecobee. Thus, we maintain that it is reasonable to assume that the likelihood of machine error is no different between customers who override and those who do not conditional on the length of time one has been subjected to modulated set-points by OEUS (a very crude proxy for device age).

SI.2.2 Bayesian Multilevel Survival Regression

Three functions of (observation) time t are core to survival modelling. These are the function for the *hazard rate* $h_i(t)$, sometimes written as $\lambda_i(t)$, the function for the *cumulative/integrated hazard rate* $H_i(t)$, and the function for the *survival/survivorship probability* $S_i(t)$. Note well that censoring is accounted for in the construction of the likelihood for survival models (i.e., the probability of the observed data given model parameters), which is based on these three functions.⁶ Accordingly, censored observations — here, records for conservation events i that were not overridden and thus ended organically or due to machine error — should not be excluded from model fitting. General forms of $h_i(t)$, $H_i(t)$, and $S_i(t)$ are respectively given in Eq. (1), Eq. (2), and Eq. (3).

$$h_i(t) = \lim_{\Delta t \rightarrow 0} \frac{P(t \leq T_i^* < (t + \Delta t) | T_i^* \geq t)}{\Delta t} \quad (1)$$

$$H_i(t) = \int_{u=0}^t h_i(u) du \quad (2)$$

$$S_i(t) = \Pr\{T_i^* \geq t\} = \exp(-H_i(t)) \quad (3)$$

⁶For discussion, see, Box-Steffensmeier and Jones (2004, p. 17-19), Brilleman et al. (2019, p. 11), Leung et al. (1997, p. 92-94), and Rodríguez (2016).

Let T_i^* indicate the true time of the occurrence of some event of interest (here, override) for a study unit (here, conservation event/hold) $i \in \{1, \dots, N\}$. For non-repeatable events of the same type (e.g., death), the probability of i experiencing the event within the time interval $[t, t + \Delta t)$ is given in the numerator of Eq. (1). This probability is conditional on i 's true event time T_i^* being greater than or equal to t . Thus, the numerator of Eq. (1) summarises the probability of the event (override) within the interval $[t, t + \Delta t)$ given that it has not occurred before the start of the interval. As a result, the hazard is, due to division by the interval width Δt in the denominator, a conditional failure rate per unit of time. However, as Δt , and thus $[t, t + \Delta t)$, shrink towards zero, an instantaneous conditional event probability is obtained for study units (conservation events/holds) at risk of the modelled event (override) at observation time t .

As seen in Eq. (3), $h_i(t)$ is related to the survival function $S_i(t_i)$ via the exponentiated, negative cumulative hazard function $H_i(t)$. The cumulative hazard is obtained by integrating the hazard rate $h_i(t)$ from some start time $u = 0$ to some moment in time t that is of interest, noting that $S_i(t_i = 0) := 1$ (Box-Steffensmeier & Jones, 2004; Rodríguez, 2016). As such, $H_i(t)$ may be thought of as the totality of risk by time t or, rather, "...the number of events that would be expected for each individual by time t if the event were a repeatable process" (Clark et al., 2003, p. 235). Note, integration is simply "fancy" addition to calculate the sum over infinitesimally small (i.e., not countable) regions of some variable, here, the area under the hazard function $h_i(t)$ with respect to time t .⁷

Keeping all of this in mind, we modelled the observed failure/censoring times T_i for each thermostat-specific conservation-event $i \in N$ using the experimental Bayesian multilevel regression framework of Brilleman and colleagues (Brilleman et al., 2020; Elçi and Brilleman, 2019; see also Brilleman et al., 2019). This framework is a part of the popular R library "rstanarm" (Goodrich et al., 2020). Formally, and continuing our borrowing of the notation of Brilleman et al. (2020, p. 3-8, 42-43), the models we estimated take the general form given in Eq. (4) in relation to the functions for the hazard (Eq. (1)), cumulative hazard (Eq. (2)), and survival probability (Eq. (3)):

$$\begin{aligned}
h_i(T_i) &= \gamma T_i^{\gamma-1} \lambda_i \\
&= \gamma T_i^{\gamma-1} \exp(\eta_i) \\
&= \gamma T_i^{\gamma-1} \exp((\beta_0 + u_{0,A} + u_{0,D} + u_{0,H}) + \beta_1 x_{1,i} + \dots + \beta_p x_{p,i}) \\
\\
H_i(T_i) &= T_i^\gamma \lambda_i \\
&= T_i^\gamma \exp(\eta_i) \\
&= T_i^\gamma \exp((\beta_0 + u_{0,A} + u_{0,D} + u_{0,H}) + \beta_1 x_{1,i} + \dots + \beta_p x_{p,i}) \\
\\
S_i(T_i) &= \exp(-H_i(T_i)) \\
&= \exp(-T_i^\gamma \lambda_i)
\end{aligned} \tag{4}$$

Here, T_i is the observed event (or censoring) time and $h_i(T_i)$, $H_i(T_i)$, and $S_i(T_i)$ are functions that provide the hazard rate, cumulative hazard rate, and survival probability with interpretations given above. Moreover, η_i is a linear predictor that relates the values of p correlates x for some observation i (e.g., temperature at event start; SL.1.3) to $h_i(T_i)$ and, by extension, $S_i(T_i)$ via $H_i(T_i)$, where, in our case, the regression coefficients β_p are *time-invariant*.

$$\begin{aligned}
h_i(T_i) &= h_0(T_i) \times \exp(\beta_1 x_{1,i} + \dots + \beta_p x_{p,i}) \\
&= \exp(\beta_0 + u_{0,A} + u_{0,D} + u_{0,H}) \gamma T_i^{\gamma-1} \times \exp(\beta_1 x_{1,i} + \dots + \beta_p x_{p,i})
\end{aligned} \tag{5}$$

⁷KEMA Inc. (2006, p. 15-16, 23, 45) provide an interesting early survival analysis of time to override using thermostat data from households in San Diego, California during demand-response events in the Summer of 2005. These events were two to five hours in length. And, for their participation, customers were paid an incentive of \$75 less \$5 each time they overrode an event.

We used varying intercepts, also known as *shared frailties* (Box-Steffensmeier & Jones, 2004; Brilleman et al., 2020; Hougaard, 2000) to account for the clustered nature of our data. Specifically, events i are nested within thermostats K which are nested within customers A who are themselves nested within geographic areas (here, ZIP Code tabulation areas) Z — where there is also the cross-nesting of customers and calendar dates D and the cross-nesting of customers and hours of the day H .

Thus, $u_{0,A}$, $u_{0,D}$, and $u_{0,H}$ are group-specific deviations from the population intercept β_0 that are specific to each customer, day, and hour-of-day (“America/Chicago” Time) $H \in \{00:00, 01:00, \dots, 22:00, 23:00\}$, respectively. As discussed by Brilleman et al. (2020, p. 6, 10), estimation of these parameters enables group-specific baseline hazard rates in line with $(\beta_0 + u_{0,A} + u_{0,D} + u_{0,H})$. However, recall from the *Main Text* (Section 2) that we excluded group-specific parameters $u_{0,K}$ for the intermediate clustering of events within thermostats and group-specific parameters $u_{0,Z}$ for the top-level clustering of accounts within ZCTAs. This was due to the customers in our analytic sample typically having just one smart thermostat. Similarly, ZCTAs typically housed just two customers in our analytic sample.

Borrowing the notation of Box-Steffensmeier and Jones (2004, p. 27), the group-centric formulation of our models can be seen in Eq. (5).

SI.2.3 Parameter Interpretation

Our analysis is not causal (IJzerman et al., 2020, Figure 2, p. 1093). And we follow Gelman et al. (2020, p. 84-85, 134) to stress the necessity of interpreting our results as predictive comparisons *between two different* study units i (i.e., holds; events). This is in contrast to a causal comparison of counterfactuals within the same study unit i .

Furthermore, each regression coefficient β_p in Eq. (4) is a *log hazard ratio* (i.e., the log of the ratio of two hazard rates). And, given the non-causal nature of our analysis, they summarise the “relative survival experience” (Clark et al., 2003, p. 236) when contrasting two different study units that differ in just one specific manner.

Put formally, a coefficient β_p is the expected difference in the *natural log* of the baseline hazard rate when comparing two study units i with values for the p th correlate x_p that differ by one and who have identical values for all other correlates (Hougaard, 2000, p. 78; Gelman et al., 2020, p. 84-85, 134). Exponentiation of the regression coefficient β_p converts it to a *hazard ratio* that summarise the expected *multiplicative difference* in the baseline hazard rate (Eq. (5)) when comparing two individuals who are identical save for their values for the correlate x_p which differs by no more than one.

SI.2.4 Distributional Form of the Baseline Hazard

A critical component of parametric survival modelling is the choice of the distributional form of the baseline hazard — i.e., the expected hazard rate when all correlates x are equal to zero (Eq. (5)) — in relation to time. This is in contrast to Cox-Proportional Hazard Models (Bradburn et al., 2003), for which the baseline hazard is left unspecified, and models that construct the baseline hazard as a smoothed function of time using regression splines (Brilleman et al., 2020; Ramsay, 1988).

There are a number of distributions with different shapes and thus divergent assumptions about risk and temporality that may be more or less realistic depending on the application area. We opted for simplicity by assuming that the baseline hazard for rejecting climatic interventions has a Weibull distribution. The Weibull is a two parameter probability distribution with *scale parameter* λ and *shape parameter* γ . The *proportional hazards* Weibull formulation of our models is clear from Eqs. (4) and (5) (Box-Steffensmeier & Jones, 2004; Brilleman et al., 2020) — where λ is defined by the linear combination of covariate values and regression coefficients encapsulated in η .

Practically speaking, use of the Weibull distribution means that our models were fit under the assumption that the baseline hazard rate changes monotonically (i.e., ever-decreasing or ever-increasing) over time. Contrast this with, for example, use of the exponential distribution (another popular choice for survival models) which would require us to assume that the baseline hazard is constant/unchanging over time.

The Weibull shape parameter λ is estimated alongside the regression coefficients — where $\gamma > 1$, $\gamma = 1$, and $\gamma < 1$ respectively indicate that the baseline hazard is monotonically increasing, constant, or monotonically decreasing. In Fig. SI.1 (SI.3.1), we show that a Weibull baseline hazard captures the general direction (decreasing) of the unconditional hazard rate (i.e., ignoring covariates) over time for our data, the latter of which we obtained non-parametrically.⁸

SI.2.5 Prior Probability Distributions for Unknown Model Parameters

Bayesian inference requires one to choose [prior distributions](#) — i.e., probability distributions that summarise information about each unknown model parameter (e.g., a regression coefficient) that is generally external to the data themselves. During estimation, these “priors” are combined with information on the plausibility of each parameter’s value given the data (i.e., the likelihood) to produce (marginal) posterior distributions. These “posteriors” are probability distributions for the possible values of each unknown model parameter (e.g., see the individual bell curves in Fig. 4).

Put simply, *a priori* beliefs about the value of a parameter is joined with information encoded in the analysed data (the likelihood) to produce “updated” beliefs about the parameter’s value in the form of a posterior distribution.

Prior probability distributions for the key parameters in Eq. (4) are listed in Eq. (6). Priors were generally chosen to be weakly-informative given regression parameters on the *natural log scale* and relatively few uncensored events (and thus less information on event times) in our data (Table SI.1). In general, narrower (i.e., “tighter”) priors (e.g., for regression coefficients β_p) were found to aid posterior sampling efficiency (Table SI.2). We also desired a degree of regularisation (i.e., parameter shrinkage) towards zero for our model with multiple multiplicative interactions (Table SI.3).

Gabry and Goodrich (2021) give technical details on their bespoke construction of priors for varying intercepts built into “rstanarm” (Goodrich et al., 2020). Briefly, this involves [decomposition of the variance-covariance matrix for the group-specific parameters](#) using a probability distribution for correlation matrices (Lewandowski et al., 2009), a multivariate probability distribution for unit-interval variables (Dirichlet), and a probability distribution for strictly positive variables (gamma). As we do not use group-specific *slopes*, this decomposition reduces to the setting of gamma priors for the standard deviation σ of each of the group-specific intercepts. The framework of Brilleman et al. (2020) does not allow estimation of correlations between group-specific intercepts.

When interpreting our prior specification, note that, before model fitting and to aid sampling efficiency, all of our quantitative and count variables (e.g., OEUS tenure, electricity consumption) were re-scaled by converting them to standardised scores (i.e., Z-scores). This involved subtracting from each variable its global sample mean (average) and then dividing by its global sample standard deviation. After this re-scaling, the mean of, say, electricity consumption is equal to a Z-score of zero and a one-unit increase in the Z-score of electricity consumption would represent the value one standard deviation above its mean.

⁸Readers unfamiliar with survival analysis should see Brilleman et al. (2020) for a brief introduction, Bradburn et al. (2003) and Clark et al. (2003) for longer, less technical treatments, and Box-Steffensmeier and Jones (2004) and Hougaard (2000) for extended technical treatments. Box-Steffensmeier and Jones (2004, ch. 3) and Hougaard (2000, ch. 2) provide comparisons of popular distributional forms for baseline hazards (e.g., exponential, Weibull, Gompertz, etc.). The writings of Bradburn et al. (2003), Brilleman et al. (2020), and Clark et al. (2003) are free and open-access.

Table SI.2: Model predictive performance using *approximate* leave-one-out cross-validation (LOO-CV).

Model Spec.	Rank	ELPD Diff. vs. 1st (S.E.)	$\hat{k} > 0.7$	Stacking Weight	\hat{R} (Max)	Bulk ESS (Min)	Tail ESS (Min)
HVAC Aware	1	0 (0)	0	0.84	1.006	1,595	3,420
HVAC Naïve	2	-73.13 (17.19)	0	0.16	1.004	1,816	3,726

Note: Both models were estimated using ten parallel chains. In each case, the sampling algorithm suffered no pathologies (i.e., “divergent transitions”). Each chain consists of 3,000 iterations. The first 1,000 iterations were devoted to “warm-up”. This resulted in a total of 20,000 post warm-up iterations (i.e., the posterior sample size) for each parameter in each model. This table reports the minimum “bulk” effective sample size (ESS) and the minimum “tail” ESS across all parameters in each model. Bulk and tail ESS are, respectively, estimates of the amount of independent information in the middle and the extremes of a posterior distribution or, rather, the posterior sample size in absence of correlation between values of each Markov chain. Vehtari et al. (2021) recommend an ESS of at least 100, although Kruschke (2015, p. 184), for example, recommends an ESS of around 10,000 when using the highest-density-type uncertainty intervals we rely on throughout this report. Convergence (i.e., the *mixing*) of chains was diagnosed using \hat{R} — i.e., the potential scale reduction factor for rank-normalised split chains (Vehtari et al., 2021). This table reports the maximum \hat{R} across all parameters in each model. Values of \hat{R} less than 1.01 are generally regarded as indicative of convergence. This table also reports the expected log point-wise predictive density (ELPD) for each model. ELPD was obtained using the approximate LOO-CV technique of Vehtari et al. (2017) and Gabry et al. (2019). ELPD is the sum of the log of the observation-specific predictive density for each of the i data points T_i in our entire sample $N = 231,344$. That is, ELPD is the sum of the log of $p(T_i|T_{-i})$ or $p(T_i)$ when the individual data point T_i (here, a specific thermostat hold) is excluded from the model. \hat{K} is a point-wise estimate of the influence of an individual observation T_i over the posterior distribution. For all N datapoints, \hat{K} should be less than or equal to 0.7 (see Gabry et al., 2019 as well as Vehtari et al., 2017). Generally, when there are data points with values for \hat{K} greater than 0.7, approximate LOO-CV may not be reliable and a model may be severely misspecified. Finally, the techniques of Yao et al. (2018) were used to obtain the “stacking weights” by jointly considering our models and assuming no single “true” model. Stacking weights are simply a simplex (i.e., a set of number that sum to unity) that maximises the ELPD when used to weight the point-wise predictions from each model in a set of candidate models. Thus, “weightier” models contribute relatively more predictive value compared to other models in the set under consideration. Given the various metrics, the flexible “HVAC Aware” model appears to win out over the “HVAC Naïve” model (Table SI.3).

$$\begin{aligned}
\beta_{1,\dots,p} &\sim \text{Normal}(\mu = 0, \sigma = 0.25) \\
\beta_0 &\sim \text{Normal}(\mu = 0, \sigma = 5) \\
\gamma_{\text{Weibull Shape}} &\sim \text{Exponential}(\lambda = 2) \\
\sigma_{\text{Group-Specific Parameters}\mu} &\sim \text{Gamma}(\alpha_{\text{Shape}} = 0.25, \beta_{\text{Scale}} = 0.25)
\end{aligned} \tag{6}$$

Readers unfamiliar with Bayesian inference should see Gelman et al. (2020, ch. 9) and van de Schoot et al. (2021) who provide thorough introductions. van de Schoot et al. (2021) also provide an [online glossary of terms commonly used by Bayesians](#). The public statistician Andrew Heiss provides a [quick, accessible rundown of key differences between frequentist and Bayesian inference](#).

SI.2.6 Model Specification and Selection

We considered two specifications of the linear predictor η in Eq. (4). The first translates the correlates used by Sarran et al. (2021, p. 4) to our research problem. This mapping is not one-to-one, however, as we adjusted our models for basic factors expected to shape the energy-related behaviour of OEUS’ customers given: (a) previous internal analyses of Octopus’ British customers; and (b) strong *a priori* expectations of Octopus stakeholders with domain expertise. Factors include a customer’s tenure with OEUS, historical consumption, historical participation in conservation events, and grid connection point.

Unlike Sarran et al. (2021), we retained energy conservation events irrespective of the operating mode of customers’ HVAC systems at event start (i.e., “Cool”, “Heat”, “Auto”, “Off”). However, to the extent that HVAC settings capture strong preferences about the state of one’s internal climate, it seems reasonable to expect the dynamics of override to unfold differently across operating modes. Therefore, our first specification features multiplicative interactions between temperature-related variables and operating mode, including one’s desired internal temperature.

Our first specification also incorporates a multiplicative interaction between internal temperature and external temperature at event start. This interaction was used to allow for possible redoubling of the association between outdoor climate on behaviour across internal conditions (e.g., “oppressive heat” one “cannot escape”). Similarly, we had no reason to expect the association between atmospheric conditions and behaviour to be linear. Indeed, the implications of heat and dew point extremes for human comfort are distinct. Thus, our first specification also includes [quadratic \(i.e., squared\) versions](#) of internal temperature, external near-surface temperature, and external near-surface dew point.

As for our second specification, a natural question is whether the substantial flexibility of the first model is warranted relative to a simpler set of correlates. Consequently, we compared our first model to a second that simply excludes all multiplicative interactions and quadratic terms involving temperature. We respectively refer to our first and second model specifications as “HVAC Aware” and “HVAC Naïve”.

Using the leave-one-observation-out-of-sample (LOO) cross-validation (CV) techniques of [Gabry et al. \(2019\)](#) and [Vehtari et al. \(2017\)](#), we compared the fitted models in terms of: (a) expected out-of-sample predictive ability; and (b) robustness to influential observations. We are not interested in out-of-sample prediction *per se* — [although we note the business utility of findings that generalise to future conservation events and, possibly, future customers and dates](#) (cf. LOO-CV with leave-one-group-out CV). Rather, [we desired a simple \(and popular\) quantitative approach to adjudicating the quality of our models and testing, in an omnibus fashion, whether our multiplicative interactions and quadratic terms are justified.](#)⁹

Our model comparison is detailed in [Table SI.2](#), where the note for this table also provides estimation settings and additional technical details on LOO-CV. Results unambiguously indicate that our model featuring multiplicative interactions between temperature and HVAC mode and quadratic terms for temperature is “best” in the sense that it is a clear improvement over our simple model. Note well that our “best” model generates fake survival probabilities that match those derived from our observed data across the range of observed follow-up times ([Fig. 2](#)).

Throughout the main text, we used our “best” model to make sense of our results, narrowly focusing on visualisations of the survival function $S_i(T_i)$ following relevant methodologists (e.g., [Box-Steffensmeier & Jones, 2004](#)). Indeed, criticism of survival models naturally lends itself to graphical displays of $h_i(T_i)$ and $S_i(T_i)$ which are easy to interpret. Such plots are especially important here as multiple multiplicative interactions complicates interpretation of point estimates ([Brambor et al., 2006](#)).

SI.3 Supplementary Results

SI.3.1 Appropriateness of the Weibull Baseline Hazard

The baseline hazard $h_0(T_i)$ is estimated as monotonically decreasing ($\gamma < 1$; [Table SI.3](#)). That is, our models indicate that the (small) instantaneous probability of override is expected to wane over time t . [Fig. SI.1](#) depicts the shape of $h_0(T_i)$ alongside a non-parametric estimate of the hazard (overlaid). The non-parametric estimate was obtained using the R library “[muhaz](#)” and it is akin to a kernel density plot using an [Epanechnikov kernel](#). The non-parametric curve is unconditional as it ignores all covariates. In contrast, $h_0(T_i)$ is conditional on covariate values being set to zero per [Eq. \(5\)](#). And, due to how we transformed our data prior to model fitting ([SI.2.5](#)), $h_0(T_i)$ relates to an energy conservation event with “typical” features — here, either the sample average (quantitative covariates) or the most-frequent category (qualitative covariates) per [Table SI.1](#).

⁹For each of the key parameters estimated under our two models, [Table SI.3](#) provides the posterior mode (PM) and the 95% highest density interval (HDI). Additionally, for each unbounded parameter (cf. standard deviations for the group-specific effects), [Table SI.3](#) provides the probability of direction (PD) — i.e., a metric summarising the proportion of the posterior distribution with the same sign as the posterior mode and thus the probability that a parameter is most likely to be positive or negative ([Makowski et al., 2019](#)).

Figure SI.1: Baseline hazard rate $h_0(T_i)$ versus unconditional hazard rate (Teal Line) over time.

Note: The curve for the baseline hazard was constructed using our “best” multilevel model (Table SI.2) of right-censored failure times and drawn as a step function using 150 equally-spaced points between 0 and 150 minutes. Baseline hazard rates are summarised using the posterior mode (i.e., the single value with the highest posterior probability; Black Line), the 68% highest posterior density interval (HDI; Inner Blue Ribbon), the 95% HDI (Red Ribbon), and the 100% HDI (i.e., the entire posterior distribution; Outer Yellow Ribbon). Each HDI (shortest probability) is the continuous range containing X% of values with the highest posterior density, where there may be a range of values with a higher probability over a discontinuous interval (Liu et al., 2015). Use of HDIs as opposed to equal-tail (i.e., quantile) intervals can result in a jagged appearance in the curve. Figure created with the aid of the R library “ggdist”.

A more flexible specification of the baseline hazard may have better captured the dip in the unconditional hazard rate circa 120-minutes post event start. However, this change presumably stems from the relatively small number of events over 120 minutes in length (Table SI.1). Still, the model-based and non-parametric baseline hazards broadly track one another. And there is clear concordance between the Kaplan-Meier survival curve and the model-based survival curve (Fig. 2), the latter of which is of course undergirded by the baseline hazard (Eqs. (4) and (5)). This agreement is generally good across the entire range of event/censoring times, pointing to the appropriateness of our “best”, Weibull-based model (Table SI.2) in terms of its ability to generate fake data that look like our observed data (i.e., posterior predictive checking).

SI.3.2 All Parameter Estimates From Fitted Models

Table SI.3: Bayesian survival models of time until override of thermostat holds, Oct. 2022 to May 2024.

	HVAC Naïve			HVAC Aware		
	Mode	95% HDI	PD	Mode	95% HDI	PD
Intercept	-6.64	[-6.74, -6.30]	1.00	-6.70	[-6.92, -6.47]	1.00
Weibull Shape Parameter Gamma	0.88	[0.87, 0.90]	—	0.88	[0.87, 0.90]	—
HVAC Mode = Auto (Ref. = Cool)	-0.14	[-0.24, -0.10]	1.00	-0.08	[-0.21, -0.07]	1.00
HVAC Mode = Heat (Ref. = Cool)	-0.08	[-0.16, 0.01]	0.95	-0.29	[-0.45, -0.15]	1.00
HVAC Mode = Off (Ref. = Cool)	-0.92	[-1.04, -0.79]	1.00	-0.86	[-1.02, -0.73]	1.00
Int. Temp. (°F) 60 Min. Prior to Event Hour (Z-Score)	0.08	[0.04, 0.11]	1.00	0.09	[0.06, 0.17]	1.00
Int. Temp. (°F) 60 Min. Prior to Event Hour (Z-Score) ²	—	—	—	-0.07	[-0.08, -0.03]	1.00
HVAC = Auto × Int. Temp. (°F) at Event Start (Z-Score)	—	—	—	-0.01	[-0.12, 0.06]	0.72
HVAC = Heat × Int. Temp. (°F) at Event Start (Z-Score)	—	—	—	0.01	[-0.16, 0.09]	0.72
HVAC = Off × Int. Temp. (°F) at Event Start (Z-Score)	—	—	—	0.12	[-0.11, 0.13]	0.54
Ext. Temp. (°F) 60 Min. Prior to Event Hour (Z-Score)	-0.02	[-0.04, 0.10]	0.77	0.11	[0.15, 0.32]	1.00
Ext. Temp. (°F) 60 Min. Prior to Event Hour (Z-Score) ²	—	—	—	0.08	[0.06, 0.15]	1.00
HVAC = Auto × Ext. Temp. (°F) 60 Min. Prior to Event Hour (Z-Score)	—	—	—	-0.07	[-0.17, 0.00]	0.98
HVAC = Heat × Ext. Temp. (°F) 60 Min. Prior to Event Hour (Z-Score)	—	—	—	-0.22	[-0.34, -0.09]	1.00
HVAC = Off × Ext. Temp. (°F) 60 Min. Prior to Event Hour (Z-Score)	—	—	—	-0.42	[-0.44, -0.10]	1.00
Int. Temp. (°F) (Z-Score) × Ext. Temp. (°F) (Z-Score)	—	—	—	0.18	[0.09, 0.18]	1.00
Ext. Dew Point (°F) 60 Min. Prior to Event Hour (Z-Score)	-0.05	[-0.09, 0.02]	0.92	0.12	[0.03, 0.16]	1.00
Ext. Dew Point (°F) 60 Min. Prior to Event Hour (Z-Score) ²	—	—	—	0.02	[0.00, 0.05]	0.96
Desired Int. Temp. (°F) - Cooling (Z-Score)	-0.08	[-0.07, -0.02]	1.00	-0.09	[-0.11, -0.03]	1.00
HVAC = Auto × Des. Int. Temp. (°F) - Cooling (Z-Score)	—	—	—	0.02	[-0.01, 0.10]	0.93
HVAC = Heat × Des. Int. Temp. (°F) - Cooling (Z-Score)	—	—	—	-0.02	[-0.07, 0.04]	0.69
HVAC = Off × Des. Int. Temp. (°F) - Cooling (Z-Score)	—	—	—	0.03	[-0.09, 0.12]	0.60
Desired Int. Temp. (°F) - Heating (Z-Score)	0.12	[0.10, 0.15]	1.00	0.14	[0.11, 0.16]	1.00
HVAC = Auto × Des. Int. Temp. (°F) - Heating (Z-Score)	—	—	—	-0.12	[-0.15, -0.04]	1.00
HVAC = Heat × Des. Int. Temp. (°F) - Heating (Z-Score)	—	—	—	0.08	[0.01, 0.18]	0.99
HVAC = Off × Des. Int. Temp. (°F) - Heating (Z-Score)	—	—	—	-0.12	[-0.10, 0.12]	0.50
Number of Holds (Any Length) Earlier On Event Day (Z-Score)	0.07	[0.06, 0.11]	1.00	0.08	[0.03, 0.09]	1.00
Hold Tenure at Event Issuance (Z-Score)	-0.11	[-0.22, -0.10]	1.00	-0.21	[-0.23, -0.11]	1.00
OEUS Tenure at Event Issuance (Z-Score)	0.00	[0.00, 0.19]	0.98	0.17	[0.00, 0.18]	0.98
Total Consumption (kWh) 60 Min. Prior to Event Hour (Z-Score)	0.06	[0.04, 0.09]	1.00	0.02	[0.02, 0.07]	1.00
ERCOT Load Zone = North (Ref. Houston)	-0.01	[-0.13, 0.19]	0.65	0.04	[-0.14, 0.18]	0.60
ERCOT Load Zone = South (Ref. Houston)	0.04	[-0.17, 0.29]	0.68	0.16	[-0.18, 0.27]	0.63
ERCOT Load Zone = West (Ref. Houston)	0.07	[-0.34, 0.20]	0.72	-0.02	[-0.27, 0.26]	0.51
St. Dev. of Varying Intercepts: Account Number	1.45	[1.20, 1.52]	—	1.30	[1.20, 1.51]	—
St. Dev. of Varying Intercepts: Calendar Day of Event	0.39	[0.29, 0.44]	—	0.29	[0.22, 0.35]	—
St. Dev. of Varying Intercepts: Hour of Day of Event	0.20	[0.06, 0.24]	—	0.28	[0.07, 0.28]	—

Note: Mode = Value with the highest posterior probability.; HDI = Continuous range containing 95% percent of values with the highest posterior density.; PD (Probability of Direction) = Share of posterior distribution with same sign as the posterior mode.

SI.4 Supplementary References

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